

SCIENCE IN THE PROCESS OF SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SPHERE

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Abstract. *In the given article the concept of sustainable economic development in the agricultural sector is discussed. The main problems of sustainable economic development of the country and the main measures to overcome these problems are presented.*

Keywords: *science, agricultural sector, sustainable economic development, sustainable development of economic sectors.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье будет рассмотрена понятие устойчивого экономического развития аграрная сфера. Представлены основные проблемы устойчивого экономического развития страны и основные меры по преодолению этих проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *наука, аграрная сфера, устойчивое экономическое развитие, устойчивое развитие отраслей экономики.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada qishloq xo'jaligida barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish konsepsiyasi muhokama qilinadi. Mamlakatni barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning asosiy muammolari va bu muammolarni bartaraf etishning asosiy chora-tadbirlari ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *fan, qishloq xo'jaligi sektori, barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish, iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarining barqaror rivojlanishi.*

It is important to mention that science began to develop in the Republic of Uzbekistan from the ancient times. Currently, scientists of the Republic of Uzbekistan are actively studying scientific research, enriching science with new discoveries, making a significant contribution to the development of world science.

A highly productive agricultural sector is the basis for the material and social well-being of society, without which its sustainable development is impossible. The problem of achieving sustainable agricultural production is one of the most important tasks in modern society.

The scientific development of the country's agricultural sector depends on the results of research. The main task of agricultural science is to introduce innovations and conduct scientific research. A developed state at a new stage of economic reforms must receive and use high-tech products from scientific activities. Traditionally, active scientific activity is a sphere of public policy.

A scientific idea always brings immediate benefits, and its use in economic activity is important. Therefore, scientific institutions switch directly to funding scientific research, even if they have a significant financial need for their scientific results. In modern conditions, the state takes upon itself the task of providing business with scientific knowledge and scientific ideas, which are one of the most important sources of the innovation process. The introduction of innovations in the agricultural sector plays an important role.

The need to develop and implement long-term plans and programs for economic growth is confirmed by the advanced experience of countries that are steadily breaking through to leading positions in the world economy and international economic relations.

Innovative development of the economy presupposes the decisive role of the state in market conditions and macroeconomic regulation. This also stimulates the active participation of the state in the distribution of resources, the organization of new production facilities and the modernization of the existing production base, the widespread attraction of foreign capital to update technologies, attract investment in fixed capital, and export finished products.

Development of scientific production Scientific production in modern conditions is considered by scientists as the most important factor in the sustainable development of the economy in scientific research work, determining the dynamic development of the country and predicting it to be one of the world leaders, which is very important in the context of the globalization of the world economy.

Identification of new directions for the implementation of economic laws and new methods for assessing specific results is the most important component of modern economic thought. Theoretical developments are presented as an integral part of long-term reform of the agricultural sector of the economy.

In the context of the development of market relations, developed scientific and technical programs for the creation of scientific products must take into account the characteristics of the life cycle, individual types of final products and be based on marketing research. This is determined by the timeliness and need to promote innovative ideas in agriculture as the basis for the formation of high-tech agricultural production.

Sustainable growth of the agricultural sector has a direct economic effect on the industry itself. The main achievements of economically developed countries include stability in the development of the agricultural sector of the economy.

The main objectives of sustainable development of the agricultural sector are to ensure control by government bodies: increasing the standard of living of the population and eliminating social stratification; improving the quality of state social infrastructure systems, such as education, healthcare, social security; development of interregional cooperation in order to reduce the export of imported products and export of raw materials; development of the country's production and innovation potential; attracting domestic and foreign investment for the development of the economy and social sphere; development and formation of state enterprises.

State policy is to support the most important scientific research, development and innovative projects for the republic in the following priority scientific areas: conducting fundamental and applied research on problems of the agricultural sector, socio-economic development, environmental protection, as well as improving the living conditions of the rural population in cooperation with leading scientific centers of the world; the development of competitive technologies, materials, research projects, equipment and technologies will contribute to a significant increase in the export potential of this country and, above all, high-tech engineering products; creation and large-scale implementation of basic technologies that ensure significant improvement in product quality, increased environmental safety, reduction of production costs and saturation of the domestic market; progressive changes in engineering and technology in order to achieve a world level of production and resource conservation sufficient to compensate for the rise in cost of raw materials, fuel and energy resources and materials; selection of highly productive varieties of agricultural crops and animals; development of new highly effective environmentally

friendly technologies for the production of agricultural products, means to combat diseases of agricultural plants and animals, as well as effective means and methods of irrigation of agricultural land; creation of highly efficient, resource-saving, environmentally friendly food production processes and technologies for processed sectors of the agro-industrial complex; development of scientific foundations and recommendations on the problems of the gradual formation of a market economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its integration into the system of world economic relations, as well as improving statehood and law in the process of transition to market relations.

Sustainable development in the future of the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan requires the implementation of state policy in the field based on new approaches. The Agriculture Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 serves as the basis for the implementation of these tasks. The main goal of this Strategy is to radically improve state policy aimed at deepening ongoing reforms aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the agri-food sector, and covers the following strategic priorities: ensuring food security of the population; development of science, education, systems of information and consulting services in agriculture; rural development.

Sustainable development of an economic system under the influence of external factors means the system's ability to ensure the balanced development of social and economic interests.

Sustainable economic growth represents the positive dynamics of macroeconomic indicators over a long period of time without significant fluctuations in their values, which is due to the constant and proportional growth of these indicators.

Sustainable social development is development that can be achieved for future generations without reducing such opportunities to meet the living needs of the present generation.

This state of the system is achieved through the balanced development of interests of different levels: achieving equilibrium of the system in the long term, taking into account economic performance and social sustainability; reducing the gap between regions of different levels of development; equality while respecting the interests of present and future generations; effective interaction of all subsystems; the ability of the entire system to self-development and self-regulation.

Formation of new directions of agribusiness based on taking into account the real demand of agricultural enterprises and, of course, experience and skills in introducing innovations in the implementation of innovative projects to solve current problems and ensuring their direct participation.

Summarizing the mentioned ideas given above it should be suggested that considering the concept of sustainable development from the perspective of various theories and studying the essence of the concept of sustainability, we can conclude that the sustainable development of the country's agricultural sector implies not only the development of its economic activity, but also an increase in the standard of living of the population through the effective use of its natural resources.

REFERENCES

1. Strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 (Appendix N. 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. UP-5853). "Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan", October 28, 2019, No. 43, Art. 815

2. Konkina V.S., Minat V.N. Methodology of economic research in the agro-industrial complex of Russia // in the collection: Current problems of science and practice of the 21st century: materials of the All-Russian scientific and practical work. conference; Ryaz fil-I NOU VO "Moscow Academy of Economics and Law". Kazan: Buk, 2016. pp. 20-25.
3. Minat V.N. Economics: textbook. manual for students studying law. Specialties // Ryazan, 2010.